

ON THE OPTIMIZATION OF TAPERED COMPOSITE LAMINATES IN PRELIMINARY STRUCTURAL DESIGN

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SUMMARY

Ply drop-offs represent preferred initiation sites for delaminations in tapered laminates. This paper presents an optimization tool, based on fracture mechanics, for the preliminary design of tapered composite laminates. The reliability and robustness of this optimization procedure is demonstrated via comparisons with finite element analysis.

Keywords: *ply drop-off, fracture mechanics, delamination, optimization.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Thickness tapering is widely employed for tailoring the specific stiffness and strength of thin-walled structural elements subjected to spatially distributed loads. Alloy plates and shells are easily tapered by machining. On the contrary the thickness tapering of composite laminates requires terminating, i.e. “dropping-off”, plies; thus, while machining alloys allows a continuous thickness variation, the tapering of composite laminates is normally performed in discrete steps. Ply drop-offs have been shown to produce stress concentrations within the laminate [1-3]; those might be severe enough to outweigh any improvement in specific stiffness and strength which is supposed to be gained by tapering the composite structural element. The stress raiser effects of ply drop-offs depend on several design variables: those include primarily the terminated ply orientation and position within the laminate, the overall laminate stacking sequence and nature of the applied load.

In principle the preliminary design of tapered laminates would require comparing a large number of candidate configurations, for which the overall thickness, position and stacking sequence of terminated plies are varied [4]; those comparative studies aim at identifying ply drop-off arrangements which avoid the onset and growth of delaminations from the terminated layers under service loading. It is easy to appreciate that the design search space comprising suitable dropping-off configurations can be vast even for relatively thin laminates; thus the optimal thickness tapering of composite structures can represent a major challenge.

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High fidelity tools such as finite element analysis (FEA) allow obtaining accurate predictions of the onset loads and propagation regime for delaminations emanating from ply drop-offs [5]; nevertheless those tools are not entirely suitable for preliminary design, since they require significant computational resources, especially when several possible alternative solutions need to be examined. In practice design guidelines for defining ply drop configurations are usually followed in order to produce robust solutions [6-8]; those rules of thumb were obtained from experimental tests, high fidelity numerical analysis and, most of all, from direct experience. Nevertheless those design guidelines provide just a qualitative indication of the expected stiffness, strength and endurance performance of a tapered composite laminate. In many practical cases, the aforementioned rules of thumb can also lead to conflicting constraints; moreover they do not provide the designer with suitable weight factors for assessing their relative importance in defining suitable ply termination configurations whenever conflicting requirements arise.

Due to the inherent difficulty in employing high fidelity tools in preliminary design and to the need to define quantitative allowables when following general dropping-off guidelines, several simplified models of tapered laminates have been introduced in the literature [9-11]. Those are essentially based on simple beam theory coupled with shear lag approximations; interlaminar stresses are typically accounted for by simulating the presence of resin rich layers between contiguous plies via sets of distributed springs or asymptotic solutions derived from two-dimensional elasticity. Those simplified models are essentially stress based, i.e. they are suitable for detecting only the onset of delaminations from ply terminations; therefore stress based models for ply drop-off analysis are typically very conservative, since delaminations may assume a stable configuration once initiated. Another key limitation of those models is that the stress field at the drop-off location may be singular [12]; this implies that proper averaging lengths/areas must be introduced in the models for defining finite stress measures at layer terminations.

In order to overcome the inherent difficulties met by stress based models, other approaches to the analysis of ply drop-offs have been based on fracture mechanics concepts [13-15]; in those models the strain energy release rate (SERR) associated with layer terminations is obtained in closed form, again applying simple beam theory. Those approaches allow in principle to take into account both the initiation and delamination propagation stages, thus leading to a robust preliminary damage tolerance design of tapered laminates. Unfortunately the SERR expressions developed so far are valid only for thick section delaminations and the effects of the tapering angle are not accounted for.

This paper presents a general formulation for deducing the SERR associated with delaminations emanating from a ply drop-off location in both the laminate thick and thin sections; the proposed methodology requires very little numerical effort when implemented and it can reliably model the effect of the tapering angle. This improved analytical method is here linked to an optimization engine which aims to find the laminate ply drop-off sequence which maximizes its damage tolerance performance under a prescribed loading condition. This paper is focused on defining an optimization strategy which allows delaying the delamination initiation, thus all the relevant SERR expression for the delaminations emanating from the resin pocket will be given in the limit of zero fracture lengths.

An optimization case study is presented in Sec. 5 and the analytical model predictions validated against FE results.

2. EQUIVALENT BEAM MODEL

It is here assumed to consider a tapered laminate in plane stress or plane strain conditions, as sketched in fig. 1. The laminate has thickness t and it comprises a set of terminated plies, whose overall thickness is H . The thick section laminate is denoted as (L). The lower continuous sub-laminate in fig. 1 is denoted as the “core” (C); the upper continuous sub-laminate is the “belt” (A). The core thickness is d ; the belt and the core sub-laminates reconnect through the thickness, so that together they constitute the thin section (R). Due to the geometric arrangement of the terminated, core and belt sub-laminates, a resin pocket is formed in the tapered section; this resin rich area is shaded in fig. 1 and it is assumed to have negligible elastic properties, i.e. it is modeled as a void. The nominal tapering angle ϕ is given as $\phi = \tan^{-1}(H/L_2)$, where L_2 is the dropping length. Delaminations are assumed to emanate from the resin pocket tips, the latter having respectively length L_1 in the thick section and L_3 in the thin one. Note that the thick section delaminations are represented as symmetric with respect to the mid-plane of the terminated block, therefore a “double” interlaminar fracture is assumed to occur there, as normally observed experimentally.

Fig. 1: idealized configuration of a ply drop-off.

All the sub-laminates which appear in the idealized configuration presented in fig. 1 are modelled as layered Euler-Bernoulli beams; the distances \bar{z}_i ($i = L, A, C, R$) represent the offset of the sub-laminate neutral axes from the individual mid-planes. The equations of elasticity for each sub-laminate beam are formulated with respect to the individual neutral axes location, thus uncoupling the membrane-bending behaviour.

Under the action of a far field axial force P and bending moment M , both defined per unit width, the laminate arrangement described above is equivalent to the three times redundant idealized beam model presented in fig. 2. The coefficients A_i and \bar{D}_i ($i = L, A, C, R$) give respectively the axial and bending stiffness of each sub-laminate with respect to the neutral axis [16]; those coefficients are defined using classical laminate theory.

In the layered Euler-Bernoulli beam approach the through-thickness orthotropic behaviour of the material is neglected. Nevertheless this can be accounted for, at least in an approximated fashion, by introducing the orthotropy rescaling [16] for the idealized configuration presented in fig. 2. Orthotropic rescaling states that all the longitudinal

dimensions in fig. 3 must be contracted by the factor $\sqrt[4]{E_3 / E_1}$, where E_1 is the equivalent longitudinal Young's modulus and E_3 is the equivalent through-thickness Young's modulus. It can be observed that, strictly speaking, orthotropic rescaling is valid for two-dimensional elasticity problems, while the beam model adopted here is essentially one-dimensional; nevertheless the effective orientation of the inclined belt segment (2), which is defined through the orthotropy rescaling, affects the stress distribution within the idealized beam configuration and therefore it must be taken into account. In other words, the effective aspect ratio of the resin pocket influences the relative magnitude of the hyper-static unknowns X_i introduced in the idealized model in fig. 2.

Fig. 2: idealized configuration of a ply drop-off.

Applying orthotropic rescaling for the longitudinal dimensions in fig. 1 one finds

$$L^*_i = \sqrt[4]{E_3 / E_1} L_i \quad (1)$$

which for $i=1,2,3$ represent the delamination and dropping section lengths in fig. 3. Due to orthotropic rescaling the effective tapering angle is given by

$$\phi^* = \tan^{-1} \frac{H}{\sqrt[4]{E_3 / E_1} L_2} \quad (2)$$

so that in general $\phi \geq \phi^*$ for standard fibre reinforced composites. The three unknowns X_i which represent the redundant sectional forces/moments for the idealized configuration in fig. 2; X_1 is the redundant axial force, X_2 is the shear force, while X_3 is the hyper-static bending moment component. Those can be found by minimizing the total complementary elastic energy associated with the Euler-Bernoulli beam assembly. This leads to the following linear system

$$\underline{\underline{A}}\{X_1 X_2 X_3\}^T = \underline{\underline{B}}\{P M\}^T \quad (3)$$

where $\underline{\underline{A}}$ and $\underline{\underline{B}}$ are matrixes of known coefficients. Here they are considered in the special case $L_1, L_3 \rightarrow 0$, which represents the onset of interlaminar damage emanating from the resin pocket.

By solving the linear system in eq. (3) it is possible to express all the axial force and bending moment components acting on the delamination tips as presented in fig. 3 in the limiting case $L_1, L_3 \rightarrow 0$

$$\begin{cases} P_{BL} = P_{BR} = X_1 + P \\ P_{TL} = P_{TR} = -X_1 \\ M_{TL} = X_3 \\ M_{BL} = M - P\left(\frac{t-d}{d} + \bar{z}_L - \bar{z}_C\right) - X_1\left(\frac{t+H}{2} + \bar{z}_A - \bar{z}_C\right) - X_3 \\ M_{TR} = X_1 H + X_2 L^*_2 + X_3 \\ M_{BR} = M - P\left(\frac{t-d}{d} + \bar{z}_L - \bar{z}_C\right) - X_1\left(\frac{t+H}{2} + \bar{z}_A - \bar{z}_C\right) - X_2 L^*_2 - X_3 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

It is worth mentioning that a general solution valid for arbitrary delamination lengths can be easily worked out. The latter is not considered here since this paper is focussed on interlaminar damage initiation.

Fig. 3: sectional resultants at the delamination tips.

3. SERR FORMULAS

The analytical approach presented by Williams [17] is here followed in order to derive the SERR expression for the thin and thick section delaminations; obtaining the SERR for the former is straightforward, while the “double” interlaminar fracture occurring at the thick section requires some additional effort, especially for working out the SERR modal components.

3.1 Thick Section Delamination

Let the following coefficients be introduced

$$\psi_A = \bar{D}_B / \bar{D}_A \quad \psi_C = \bar{D}_C / \bar{D}_B \quad (5)$$

where \bar{D}_i is the bending stiffness of the sub-laminate i (A: belt; B: terminated block; C: core). The bending moment contribution to the mode I and mode II SERR for the thick section “double” delamination can be expressed as follows

$$G_I^{(M)} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{M_{IA}^2}{\bar{D}_A} + \frac{M_{IC}^2}{\bar{D}_C} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$G_{II}^{(M)} = \frac{1}{4} \left[M_{II}^2 \left(\frac{1 + \psi_A}{\bar{D}_A} + \frac{\psi_A^2 \psi_C^2}{\bar{D}_C} \right) - \frac{M^2}{\bar{D}_L} \right]$$

where

$$M_{IA} = \frac{M_{TL} \psi_A (1 + \psi_C) - M_{BL}}{\psi_A (1 + \psi_C) + 1} \quad (7)$$

$$M_{IC} = \frac{\psi_A \psi_C M_{TL} - (1 + \psi_A) M_{BL}}{\psi_A (1 + \psi_C) + 1}$$

$$M_{II} = \frac{M_{TL} + M_{BL}}{\psi_A (1 + \psi_C) + 1}$$

The axial force produces only a mode II SERR component [17], whose expression for the thick section delamination is found to be

$$G_{II}^{(P)} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{P_{TL}^2}{A_A} + \frac{P_{BL}^2}{A_C} - \frac{P^2}{A_L} \right) \quad (8)$$

where A_i is the axial stiffness of the sub-laminate i (A: belt; C: core, L: thick section). Finally when the shear force $X_2 < 0$ it produces a mode I opening component on the thick section double delamination; this can be evaluated as follows

$$G_I^{(T)} = \frac{3}{5} X_2^2 \left[\frac{1}{G_A (t - H - d)} + \frac{1}{G_C d} \right] \quad (9)$$

where G_A is the through thickness shear modulus of the belt sub-laminate and G_C that of the core sub-laminate.

The total mode I and mode II SERR for the thick section delamination are found by adding up the axial force, bending moment and shear contributions in eqs. (6), (8) and (9); this leads to the following expressions

$$\begin{aligned} G_I &= G_I^{(M)} + G_I^{(T)} \\ G_{II} &= G_{II}^{(P)} + G_{II}^{(M)} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

3.2 Thin Section Delamination

The bending moment acting on the thin section is given by

$$M_R = M - P(H/2 + \bar{z}_L - \bar{z}_R) \quad (11)$$

Let the following coefficient be introduced

$$\psi_R = \bar{D}_C / \bar{D}_A \quad (12)$$

The mode I and mode II SERR components in this case are given as follows

$$\begin{aligned} G_I^{(M)} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\psi_R M_{TR} - M_{BR}}{1 + \psi_R} \right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{\bar{D}_A} + \frac{1}{\bar{D}_C} \right) \\ G_{II}^{(M)} &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{M_{TR} + M_{BR}}{1 + \psi_R} \right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{\bar{D}_A} + \frac{\psi_R^2}{\bar{D}_C} \right) - \frac{M_R^2}{\bar{D}_R} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Again the axial force produces only a mode II component at the thin section end

$$G_{II}^{(P)} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{P_{TR}^2}{A_A} + \frac{P_{BR}^2}{A_C} - \frac{P^2}{A_R} \right) \quad (14)$$

For the thin section delamination there is an additional mode I SERR contribution due to shear if $X_2 > 0$. This has the same expression as in eq. (9), therefore in this case the overall SERR components can be found by substituting eqs. (9), (13) and (14) into eq. (10)

4. THE OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

The SERR analytical expressions worked out in Sec. 3 allow detecting the onset of delaminations in both the thick and thin section by using any suitable energetic fracture criterion. For example assuming linear interaction between the modal components one can postulate that fracture occurs when

$$\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}} \geq 1 \quad (15)$$

where G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} are the critical SERR respectively in pure mode I and pure mode II. The left hand side of eq. (15) can be considered as a failure index, which needs to be minimized in order to maximize the static strength and fatigue endurance of an arbitrary laminate which comprises layer terminations.

Considering that tapered laminates have multiple ply drop-offs, the general optimization problem with respect to layer terminations in two dimensional plane stress or plane strain conditions can be stated in the following form: *given prescribed “thick” and “thin” section stacking sequences find the ply drop-off configuration which allows minimizing the maximum failure index value when tapering the laminate from the “thick” to the “thin” sections under assigned far field axial and bending loads, i.e.*

$$\min \left[\max_{i=1,2,\dots,N} \left(\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}} \right)_i \right] \quad (16)$$

where i is the ply-drop identifier and N is the total number of ply drops. The optimization problem statement is summarized in fig. 4; the laminate tapering in principle requires changing both the thickness and the stacking sequence passing from the thick section “R” to the thin section “T”.

Fig. 4: statement of the optimization problem; bending moments and axial forces act on the sections R and T.

It is worth remarking that the optimization problem stated above is essentially topological; it is required to find which plies need to be dropped in order to “match” the thick section laminate with the thin one, i.e. obtaining the prescribed thin section stacking sequence by progressively “subtracting” plies from the thick one. Once those plies have been identified it is necessary to state in which order the layers have to be terminated; this actually defines “where” the drop-offs are in topological sense, i.e. relative to each other.

4.1 The Critical Interaction Distance

Provided that no external shear forces are applied on the end sections and that no distributed surface loads act between the thick section and the thin one, the analytical SERR expressions worked out in Sec. 3 apply to each of the drop-offs. On the other hand for the SERR expression to hold it is also necessary that the ply terminations do not interact with each other, i.e. they must be elastically “isolated”; in a geometric perspective this condition is equivalent to stating that the overall tapered section length L in fig. 4 must be infinite, which is clearly too restrictive in practical cases. Nevertheless Cui and Wisnom [18] have demonstrated that there exists a critical distance S_c beyond which ply terminations can be considered as not interacting; this is due to the fact that the load carried by terminated plies is redistributed onto the surrounding layers through shear stresses, whose magnitude cannot exceed in the first approximation the shear yields stress τ_Y of the resin phase. Although the existence of a critical distance for interaction has been demonstrated experimentally only for axial load cases, it is easy to extend the shear lag approach developed in [18] to mixed axial force/bending cases, as sketched in fig. 5; the interaction distance is given by

$$S_c = \frac{1}{\tau_Y H} \left[\left| \overline{M}_B \right| + \overline{P}_B \left(\frac{H}{2} - \frac{\left| \overline{M}_B \right|}{\overline{M}_B} z_B \right) \right] \quad (17)$$

where \overline{P}_B and \overline{M}_B are respectively the far field axial force and bending moment carried by the terminated block. The interaction distance in eq. (17) can be computed for each ply termination within the laminate. Nevertheless it is important to observe that ply drop-offs can interact as assumed when deriving eq. (17) only when contiguous plies are terminated; if the plies are interleaved even by a single continuous layer, the effect of the stress interaction is strongly reduced.

Fig. 5: extended shear lag approximation for calculating the interaction distance.

The actual distance between ply terminations is established by geometrical constraints; the layers are required to fill the volume comprised between the mould surfaces and this dictates the actual spatial location of ply drop-offs. Those geometrical constraints are not accounted for in the purely topological optimization approach considered here and this constitutes the main limitation of the proposed methodology. Nevertheless it must be

considered that the interaction distances for a given loading conditions can be estimated “a posteriori”, i.e. after the optimization task is completed; this allows estimating an applied load level beyond which the predictions of the analytical SERR formulas are not reliable any more since some of the ply drop-offs are interacting. In this case the optimization results are valid up to the load level which marks the first interaction among consecutive drop-offs. It must also be noted that the last statement is quite conservative; the concept of interaction distance is strictly valid when ply drop-offs are consecutive and contiguous, while interleaving quickly damps out any mutual interaction.

4.2 First Optimization Stage

The first stage of the optimization process is based on defining which plies have to be dropped. Tapering the thick section to the thin one implies that multiple instances of the thin laminate can exist within the thick one. Among all the possible choices, the preferred one is that which allows dropping the innermost plies; this is motivated by the fact that in bending the innermost plies are the less loaded. This is not typically the best choice in pure tension, but it must be considered that ply drops on the surface are usually subjected to large peeling stresses, so they must be avoided. Moreover when layer terminations are close to the surface they can also experience other damage mechanisms which are not accounted for here due to the simple loading distribution which has assumed for working out the SERR formulas; a typical case is represented by impacts. A simple deterministic algorithm has been developed to perform this first optimization task; the thick and thin laminates are scanned progressively from the outer layers to the inner ones. Plies having corresponding angles are assumed continuous, while layers for which the orientations do not match are terminated; the “out-in” scanning ends when the full thin section laminate has been identified within the thick one. An example of the procedure described above is presented in fig. 6.

4.3 Second Optimization Stage

Once the terminated plies have been identified, it is necessary to specify the sequence in which they have to be dropped-off; note that if N ply terminations are required, there exist $N!$ possible sequences. This implies that, even for the simple case presented in fig. 6, there are about 5×10^8 possible different orders in which the terminations can be arranged. In order to produce an optimized dropping-off sequence it is necessary to explore such a large search space, where multiple local minima are present. Actually this second stage of the optimization problem represents a classical instance of the “Travelling Salesman Problem”; the ply drop-off order can be regarded as a sequence of locations to be “visited” in a metric space where the distance operator is defined by the failure index on the left hand side of eq. (15).

A probabilistic meta-heuristic optimization method, namely simulated annealing with stochastic tunnelling [19-20], has been implemented to perform the second optimization stage described above. This algorithm offers relatively fast convergence and robustness and it is also intrinsically parallel.

Fig. 6: deterministic algorithm for finding the innermost ply drop-off sequence; thick laminate to the left, thin laminate to the right; terminated plies are pointed by the green arrows; scanning direction is from top to bottom (out-in, red arrow).

5. A VALIDATION CASE STUDY

The validation case study selected for the optimization process described in Sec. 4 is sketched in fig. 7. A symmetric tapered laminated subjected to pure bending is considered; the tapering involves both halving the laminate thickness and changing the relative stacking sequence composition. It has been assumed that the laminate is made of T300/914C CFRP, whose mechanical properties, fracture toughness included, are given in tab. 1. It is assumed that the fracture criterion for the aforementioned material is given by the simple linear interaction rule in eq. (15).

In the validation procedure two cases are compared; the first is a drop-off sequence defined by the typical tapering guidelines presented in the literature [6-8]. The second tapered lay-out has been obtained using the optimization algorithm described in Sec. 4. In both cases the innermost plies have been terminated, so that the difference between the two tapering sequences is only in the ply drop-off order.

Thick Section Stacking Sequence: $[0^\circ/90^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ]_{3S}$

Thin Section Stacking Sequence: $[0^\circ/0^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ]_{3S}$

Fig. 7: validation case study.

5.1 Configuration Based On Literature Design Guidelines

Summarizing the design guidelines presented in Refs. [6-8], the following drop-off rules are here adopted:

- 1) maintain laminate symmetry [6-7];
- 2) drop-off inner plies first [7];
- 3) drop 0° plies close to the thick section [8];
- 4) drop $\pm 45^\circ$ plies between the thick and the thin sections [8];
- 5) drop 90° plies close to the thin section [8]
- 6) avoid dropping 0° plies adjacent to 90° plies [7];
- 7) promote interleaving whenever possible [6];

The resulting laminate configuration is denoted as “Case A” and presented in fig. 8.(a); it can be observed that all the rules listed above have been successfully applied. It is worth observing that this may not be always the case; depending on the thick and thin section stacking sequences some of the aforementioned rules can lead to conflicting requirements. In this case it would be extremely difficult to apply the guidelines in a strict sense and a fuzzy logic approach should be preferred; nevertheless the robustness of the procedure remains questionable, since, as mentioned before, proper weight factors should be applied to the drop-off rules in order to rank the importance of each guideline whenever conflicting requirements arise.

5.2 Optimized Configuration

The tapered laminated optimized configuration, denoted as “Case B”, is presented in fig. 8.(b). In this specific case none of the rules listed above has been directly applied. The configuration has been obtained running the two stage optimization process whereby the best dropping-off sequence has been established by minimizing the maximum ply

termination failure index, as postulated in eq. (16). The differences with the (A) configuration are quite striking: first of all the intermediate laminate sections are asymmetric. Symmetry is kept only at the thick and thin ends, where the stacking sequence is fixed by the user; no ply drops are present in the upper region of the laminate close to the thin end; due to the applied load this zone of the tapered beam is subjected to axial compression. Some of the 0° plies are terminated close to the thin section end, but either close to the laminate neutral axis or in the region subjected to tensile axial strains.

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_1 &= 142.4 \text{ GPa} & E_2 = E_3 &= 8.7 \text{ GPa} \\
 G_{12} = G_{13} &= 4.6 \text{ GPa} & G_{23} &= 3.8 \text{ GPa} \\
 \nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = \nu_{23} &= 0.3 \\
 G_{Ic} &= 0.36 \text{ N/mm} & G_{IIc} &= 0.9 \text{ N/mm}
 \end{aligned}$$

Tab. 1: assumed mechanical properties for T300/914C.

Fig. 8.(a): Case A configuration, obtained from the literature design guidelines.

Fig. 8.(b): Case B configuration, obtained from the optimization process.

It is therefore clear that the tapering configuration defined via the optimization process violates some of the design guidelines suggested in the literature, namely the symmetry of the laminate and most importantly the drop-off ordering based on the ply angle.

5.3 FE Analysis

In order to validate the output of the optimization engine it is necessary to verify if the (B) configuration exhibits a larger strength than the case (A) design. This task is here accomplished through virtual testing using LS-DYNA as the explicit FE solver; both case (A) and (B) laminates have been modelled on a ply-by-ply level with solid elements; the mesh across the specimen width comprises a single element. Solid cohesive elements [21-23] have been introduced at each interface along the whole layer lengths. The presence of resin pockets at the drop-off locations is simulated by triangular elements having the unreinforced resin mechanical properties. Damage is accumulated in the interface elements according to a mixed-mode bi-linear cohesive law derived from the interaction criteria in eq. (15). When the interface element local damage index attains a unit value it means that the elastic energy spent in deforming the interface equals the mixed-mode fracture toughness, so that the interface is considered fully failed; this conditions marks the onset of a macroscopic delamination. Homogenized through-thickness mechanical properties have been assumed for the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. The FE modelling methodology described above has been validated against a wide set of numerical and experimental cases and it provides a reliable benchmark in terms of virtual testing.

The results of the FE analysis are presented in fig. 9.(a) for the case (A) configuration and in fig. 9.(b) for the case (B) layout. The case (A) tapered beam fails at the ply drop-off location which is closest to the laminate thin section, in the region where the far field bending moment induces axial compressive strains. Despite the fact that the dropped-ply at the aforementioned location has a 90° orientation, the associated SERR is large enough to fail the interface and create a delamination which then experiences unstable growth for a small load increment.

Fig. 9.(a): Case A configuration: damage index plots at failure load, $M = 2500$ Nmm.

Fig. 9.(b): Case B configuration, damage index plots at failure load, $M = 3000 \text{ N.m}$.

For the case (B) scenario the onset of failure is completely different; no ply drops are present in the beam compressed top half close to the thin end, so the failure mode seen for the case (A) configuration is completely suppressed. A delamination onset occurs from a $+45^\circ$ ply drop-off close to the thin end, but in this case the interlaminar fracture is stable; on the other hand an unstable delamination initiates in the upper laminate half almost in between the thick and thin sections. Also in this case the unstable interlaminar fracture emanates from the resin pocket associated with a 90° ply termination.

For both case (A) and case (B) the analytical solution predicts correctly the position of the weakest ply drop-off location..

The failure load for the case (B) scenario is 20% higher than for the case (A) configuration and this proves the robustness of the proposed optimization approach. Applying the analytical SERR formulas to each individual ply drop-off comprised in both the configurations also allows estimating the specimen failure load via purely analytical means. The results of this assessment are presented in tab. 2.

Configuration	LS-DYNA (N)	Analytical (N)
(A)	2500	1995 (-20.2 %)
(B)	3000	3270 (+9%)

Tab. 2: comparison of delamination initiation load between the FE model and the analytical solution

5.4 Discussion

Summarizing the results found so far, it can be observed that the analytical optimization method proposed in this paper is able to capture correctly and most importantly mitigate the failure modes associated with the onset of delaminations from ply drop-offs. Actually the analytical SERR formulas also provide a good assessment of the delamination initiation load even in the presence of multiple ply drops in moderately thick laminates, as in the case study above. The analytical SERR formulas are conservative in terms of the delamination

initiation load for the non optimized configuration; this is due to the fact that the resin pockets are actually considered as voids in the analytical model, so the local stiffening effect of the matrix phase at the drop-off location is neglected. On the contrary the damage initiation load for the optimized lay-up is actually slightly overestimated; this might be due to the fact that the critical delamination initiation for the case (B) configuration occurs in a thicker region of the laminate with respect to case (A). It has to be expected that the thicker the section, the less accurate the beam assumption on which the SERR formulas are based. This may clearly lead to an underestimation of the local failure index for the case (B) scenario, since shear deformation can play a significant role.

Applying the critical distance expression in eq. (17) to the ply drops in both case (A) and case (B), the analytical approach predicts that no elastic interaction occurs between contiguous ply drops; this result is also confirmed by the FE stress plots.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Closed form expressions for the strain energy release rate (SERR) associated with delaminations emanating from ply drop-offs in tapered composite laminates have been obtained using Euler-Bernoulli beam theory; those formulas are valid both in plane stress and plane strain, provided that consistent reduced material coefficients are considered. The SERR expressions are valid for non-interacting, i.e. elastically isolated, ply terminations. An expression for the critical staggering distance between contiguous ply drop-offs has been introduced; if the distance between two terminations exceeds the critical staggering length, the ply drop-offs can be considered as elastically isolated.

A topological optimization method for maximizing the damage tolerance performance of tapered laminates has been presented and discussed; this approach is based on the SERR formulas mentioned above and it is strictly valid if the critical staggering distances are not exceeded due to geometrical or load constraints. The optimization method comprises two distinct stages; the first is purely deterministic and it allows identifying which plies need to be dropped in order to obtain a prescribed laminate stacking sequence at the thin end. The second optimization stage defines which is the optimal dropping sequence and it is based on a probabilistic meta-heuristic algorithm, namely simulated annealing with stochastic tunneling.

Comparisons with high fidelity FE results for a simple tapered beam configuration under pure bending have demonstrated that the proposed optimization method is robust and reliable; the optimized solution is significantly stronger than an alternative configuration defined by using standard design guidelines from the literature. The predicted strength values for the tapered laminate configurations considered here were in reasonably good agreement with the FE results.

Anyway the optimization tool presented here is not meant to be employed as a means for accurately assessing the strength of tapered laminates; the main aim here is providing a tool for performing quick comparative assessments among various laminate lay-ups in a preliminary design stage, i.e. when the requirements for modest computational times are more important than ultimate accuracy. In order to provide a comparison in terms of computational efficiency, it is worth stressing that the analytical optimization method takes

a few minutes to run on a standard desktop computer, while the LS-DYNA models require several hours to run.

Further validation cases need to be considered in order to assess the method's reliability in mixed axial tension/compression and bending cases.

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